

Impact of Micro Irrigation on Cropping Pattern in Vaijapur Tehsil of Aurangabad District

Dr. Someshwar Narayan Babar¹, Dr. Yogita Kisanrao Rahane², Dr. Manisha Baburao Surase³,
Dr. D. R. Ghodke⁴

¹Head, Department of Economics, Vinayakrao Patil Mahavidyalaya, Vaijapur Dist. Aurangabad.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Vinayakrao Patil Mahavidyalaya, Vaijapur Dist. Aurangabad.

³Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Vinayakrao Patil Mahavidyalaya, Vaijapur Dist. Aurangabad.

⁴Associate Professor, Department of Commerce, Vinayakrao Patil Mahavidyalaya, Vaijapur Dist. Aurangabad.

Corresponding author- Dr. Someshwar Narayan Babar

Email- babarsn@gmail.com

Abstract

Micro-irrigation gained prevalence when the Parliament was rocked with issue of farmer suicides. Sensing the significance and probable benefits of the process to double the farmers' income along with agricultural sustainability and environmental quality, the Union government launched a comprehensive flagship programme called *Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchai Yojana* or "more crop per drop". Micro-irrigation can increase yields and decrease water, fertiliser and labour requirements. Present study found that in Vaijapur taluka cotton is the most widely grown crop, followed by maize, onion, Bajri, Gram, and wheat in Vaijapur Tehsil. This study also found that the percentage of cultivated land of Vaijapur taluka to the total cultivated land of Aurangabad district and coverage area under micro irrigation has been increased. According to the respondents, some minor changes occurred in cropping pattern due to MIS in Vaijapur taluka. Changes in cropping patterns and the use of micro irrigation methods for land cultivation are suggested as remedies for the water management in drought prone area.

Key words: Micro Irrigation, coverage area, Cropping Pattern

Introduction:

Micro-irrigation gained prevalence when the Parliament was rocked with issue of farmer suicides. Sensing the significance and probable benefits of the process to double the farmers' income along with agricultural sustainability and environmental quality, the Union government launched a comprehensive flagship programme called *Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchai Yojana* or "more crop per drop".

Under the programme, financial assistance of up to 55 per cent is available for small and marginal farmers and 45 per cent for other farmers for adoption of micro-irrigation systems. The funding pattern between the Union governments and the state government's share since November 2015 has been 60:40 for all states except the North East and the Himalayan states, for which the funding pattern is 90:10.

Micro-irrigation can increase yields and decrease water, fertiliser and labour requirements. By applying water directly to the root zone, the practice reduces loss of water through conveyance, run-off, deep percolation and evaporation.

Objectives:

1. To study the impact of MIS on cropping patterns in the study area.
2. To suggest measures for water management in drought prone area.

Research Methodology:

In the present study, primary and secondary data are used. For the purpose of this study, primary data is collected through a schedule questioner. In this study, we selected 450 farmers from 30 villages in Vaijapur tehsil in Aurangabad district. Secondary data from authentic sources was collected about the cultivated area of various crops and products as well as rainfall in the study area. For analysis, statistical tools such as percentage & average have been used in the present study.

Review of Literature:

Dhawan B. D. & Harsharan Singh Datta (1992)²² examined the irrigation impact on multiple cropping pattern. The multiple regression analysis shows that the close relationship between irrigation development and the rise in intensity of cropping at the all-India level. The regression analysis across 14 states for the pooled data for the period 1983-84 to 1987-88 throws up a value of the impact of irrigation on intensity of cropping, namely, 0.46, that is very near the predicted value of 0.48. But the time series analysis for the period 1950-51 to 1987-88 reveals a somewhat higher impact value of irrigation, namely, 0.65 percentage points rise in intensity of cropping corresponding to percentage point rise in the irrigation ratio as defined in this paper. It is believed that this estimate of the irrigation impact is biased upwards because of the

omission of variables like tractorisation from the regression model. Therefore, the estimate based on cross-sectional analysis is most probably nearer the true value. Pooled cross-sectional analysis for different periods over 35-year time span of 1953-54 to 1987-88 does not sustain the thesis of decline in the all-India impact of irrigation on intensity of cropping with the passage of time. In fact, weak signs of improvement in this impact are discernible. Exercises into assessing comparative impact by type of irrigation have not yielded meaningful results. Whereas tank irrigation turns out to be with an incredibly high positive impact on intensity of cropping during the course of time series analysis, it comes out with a negative sign in the cross-sectional results. This calls for further enquiry to verify the veracity of the general impression that the irrigation impact on intensity of cropping rises as we move from tank irrigation to canal irrigation, and onto well irrigation.

Bhaskar K.S., Rao M.R.K., Mendhe P.N. and M.R. Suryavanshi (2005) ³ examined the water management in cotton. They have been carried out this research work at different Agricultural Universities in Maharashtra (Rahuri, Purbhani and Akola), Cotton Research Station, Navsari, and ICAR Institutes, Agricultural Research farms and farmers fields during the past few years. In cotton, vegetables and horticultural crops the micro irrigation system gives the above 90 per cent irrigation efficiency with increasing yield and quality. The 55.40 per cent area covered under

Table No 1 Status of rainfall in Aurangabad District
 (Base Year – 2021-22)

Sr. No.	Taluka	Average		In 2021		Percentage
		Rainfall Day's	Rainfall (mm)	Rainfall Day's	Rainfall (mm)	
1	Kannad	70	1007.3	67	1291.7	28.2
2	Soegaon	54	1084.9	62	1267.6	16.8
3	Sillod	59	793.2	68	1232.5	55.4
4	Phulambri	59	950.8	54	850.7	-10.5
5	Aurangabad	76	1246.1	62	965.0	-22.6
6	Khuldabad	75	1295.0	69	1236.9	-4.5
7	Vaijapur	77	928.9	66	1017.3	9.5
8	Gangapur	71	1143.9	67	1036.3	-9.4
9	Paithan	72	1173.6	59	1179.7	0.5
	Aurangabad District	68	1069.3	64	1120	4.7

Source: Aurangabad District Socio-Economic Review, 2022. Table no 1 shows that the average rainfall of Aurangabad district was 1069.3 mm and 68 days and average rainfall in Vaijapur taluka was 928.9 mm and rainfall 77 days in 2021-22.

2. Cropping Pattern in Vaijapur Tehsil:

The proportion of area under different crops at a particular time is called a cropping pattern. A change in cropping pattern implies a change in the

micro irrigation is in horticultural crops. The drip irrigation system has been given higher saving of water and quality yield. The area under micro-irrigation is increasing compare to previous years, due to water saving and water use efficiency.

Karunakaran K.R., & Palanisami K. (1998) ¹³ explored the Impact of Irrigation on Cropping Intensity, which shows that the close relationship between irrigation development and cropping intensity at state level. Study also indicate the positive impact of different irrigation sources (such as canal, tank irrigation and dug well irrigation) on cropping intensity up to 1979-80. Later on, tube-well and dug well irrigation has indicates the more impact on intensity of crop. The tank irrigation declining trend shows the positive impact on cropping intensity. Study suggests that, it is necessary to invest the minimum amount per hectare on tank irrigation over the major and medium irrigation projects.

Result and Discussion:

1. Status of Rainfall:

Marathwada has always been prone to droughts. Rainfall variability and water scarcity are the major issues in the semi-arid Marathwada region of Maharashtra. With 24 out of 36 districts in Maharashtra facing deficient monsoon and the situation worsening in the drought-hit Marathwada and Vidarbha regions, the State government has decided to go for cloud seeding. Eighteen districts, mainly in Marathwada and Vidarbha, were facing a monsoon deficit of 20-51 per cent in July 2019.

proportion of area under different crops. Cropping patterns in any region depend upon the physical characteristics of the soil, climate, weather, rainfall etc. It also depends upon the nature and availability of irrigation facilities and institutional facilities as well. Economic motivations such as prices and income maximization, farm size, insurance against risk, availability of inputs and land tenure systems also factor into the determination of cropping

patterns. The conditions of the soil and climate in the Marathwada region are such that they contribute to a low value crop pattern and relatively low yields for most of the significant crops.

The major crops grown in the Vaijapur taluka of Aurangabad district during the kharif season are jowar, soybean, cotton, tur, mung, urid etc.; during

rabi season gram, safflower, sugarcane, rabi jowar, etc. Vegetables like tomatoes, peppers, onions, and brinjal are also cultivated in the summer. Among the main crops of the region are horticultural crops like mangoes and oranges, which are produced by irrigated horticulture. In summer, they also grow watermelons and ground nuts.

Table No 2 Cropping Pattern of Vaijapur Taluka of Aurangabad district

Crop	Gross Cropped area (in ha) 2019-20	Gross Cropped area (in ha) 2021-22
Wheat	6663	11042
Jowar	6273	3897
Bajri	6670	4969
Maize	31515	44619
Gram	6489	9090
Toor	1561	2295
Sugarcane	975	2195
Onion	9152	9152
Brinjal	63	32
Tomato	100	115
Cotton	73940	63297
Chili	88	64
Fruits & vegetables	11918	2896
Spices	773	915
Total Cultivated land of Vaijapur Taluka	153534 (15.73%)	168525 (16.37%)
Total Cultivated land of Aurangabad District	975770	1030310

Note: Bracket figure indicates percentage to total cultivated land of Aurangabad district.

Source: Aurangabad District Socio-Economic Review, 2020.

Table no 2 indicates that the gross cropped area under cotton is highest (73,940 ha) and followed by maize 31515 ha, onion 9152 ha, Bajri 6670 ha, Gram 6489 ha, wheat 6363 ha, Jowar 6273 ha etc. in Vaijapur taluka in the year 2020. This table also indicates that the percentage of cultivated land of Vaijapur taluka to total cultivated land of Aurangabad district is 15.73 percent and the total cultivated land of Aurangabad is 975770 ha in the year 2019-20.

3. Crop wise Coverage Area under Micro Irrigation:

According to the MIS Physical achievement Report 2019-20, Marathwada region as well as Maharashtra state, cotton, sugarcane and turmeric are produced by using the drip irrigation method. The fruit crops like banana, grapes, mango, pomegranate, orange, sweet lime (mosambi) are produced under drip irrigation method. The groundnut, jowar, bajra, gram, soybean, and maize are produced under sprinkler irrigation method. In Aurangabad district, gross coverage area of micro irrigation was 12216.4 ha, out of them 11050.6 ha under drip irrigation and 1165.84 ha under sprinkler irrigation method in 2019-20.

The crop wise coverage area under micro irrigation in Vaijapur tehsil of Aurangabad district is given in table 3.

Onion:

The coverage area of cotton crop is highest under micro irrigation method in Vaijapur tehsil of Aurangabad district. In 2019-20, it was 1408.68 ha, out of which 122.54 ha under drip & 1286.14 ha under sprinkler irrigation method.

Cotton:

In 2019-20, it was 614.98 ha, out of which 242.1 ha under drip & 372.88 ha under sprinkler irrigation method.

Maize:

In 2019-20, the coverage area of sugarcane crop under micro irrigation was 114.93 ha, out of which 43.41 ha was under drip irrigation and 71.52 ha under sprinkler irrigation in Vaijapur tehsil of Aurangabad district.

Sugarcane:

In 2019-20, the coverage area of sugarcane crop under micro irrigation was 190.16 ha, out of which 271.12 ha was under drip irrigation and 0.4 ha under sprinkler irrigation in Aurangabad district. In 2019-20 total coverage area of micro irrigation was 2987.17 ha, out of them 1049.95 ha under drip irrigation and 1937.22 ha under sprinkler irrigation method. In short area under sprinkler irrigation method is highest in Vaijapur tehsil, it was 64.85 percent.

Table3 Crop wise Area under Micro Irrigation in Aurangabad District (2019-20)
 (Area in ha)

Crops	Drip	Sprinkler	Total
Cotton	242.1	372.88	614.98
Onion	122.54	1286.14	1408.68
Maize	43.41	71.52	114.93
Wheat	0	31.48	31.48
Sugarcane	190.16	0	190.16
Other Crops	451.74	175.2	626.94
Total	1049.95 (35.15)	1937.22 (64.85)	2987.17 (100)

Source: Access through https://pmksy.gov.in/microirrigation/Report_Crop.aspx; on March 2023

4. Opinion of the Respondent Farmers about MIS:

According to table no 4, 70.67 percent of respondents experienced Saves water and produces higher yields. 76.89 percent reported changes in

crop patterns, Due to the MIS, Electricity consumption has been reduced for 294 respondents, and 76.89 percent respondents told the changes in cropping patterns due to the MIS. In short, according to the respondents, some minor changes occurred in cropping pattern due to MIS in Vaijapur taluka.

Table No 4 Respondent Farmers Opinion About Micro Irrigation System

Opinion	Responses	Percentage
Electricity consumption has been reduced	294	65.33
Saves water and produces higher yields	318	70.67
Coverage area of irrigation has been increased	309	68.67
Seed germination is improved	276	61.33
It is not necessary to level the fields	258	57.33
The operation and maintenance cost increases due to damages done by animals and mishandling of MI set.	312	69.33
Initial investment cost is high	372	82.67
Changes in cropping patterns	346	76.89

Source: Field survey, April & May 2022

5. Measures for Water Management in Drought Prone Area:

According to table no. 5, the majority of respondents (372) suggested that water should be used properly for irrigation; 60.67 percent respondents suggested micro irrigation, which is

drip and sprinkler irrigation; 43.11 percent respondents suggested using farm pond water for irrigation; 46 percent respondents suggested making the planning of rain water storage for irrigation, and 172 respondents suggested cultivation of low water growing crop.

Table No 5 Respondent Farmers Opinion about Water Management in Drought Prone Area

Opinion	Responses	Percentage
Use of micro irrigation	273	60.67
Water should be used properly for irrigation	372	82.67
Using farm pond water for irrigation	194	43.11
Planning of rain water storage for irrigation	207	46.00
Cultivation of low water growing crop	172	38.22

Source: Field survey, April & May 2022

Conclusion:

Present study found that in Vaijapur taluka during Kharif season are jowar, soybean, cotton, tur, mung, urid, etc. and during rabi season gram, safflower, sugarcane, rabi jowar, etc. Vegetables like tomato, chilli, brinjal, and onion are also

cultivated in the summer season. Cotton is the most widely grown crop, followed by maize, onion, Bajri, Gram, and wheat in Vaijapur Tehsil. This study also found that the percentage of cultivated land of Vaijapur taluka to the total cultivated land of Aurangabad district is only 15.73 percent in the year 2019-20. According to the respondents, some minor

changes occurred in cropping pattern due to MIS in Vaijapur taluka. Changes in cropping patterns and the use of micro irrigation methods for land cultivation are suggested as remedies for the water management in drought prone area.

Acknowledgments:

Authors are thankful to The Principal, Vinayakrao Patil Mahavidyalaya, Vaijapur and University Grants Commission (UGC), New Delhi, for providing financial assistance under STRIDE (Component I).

References:

1. Ram L. Ray, Ali Fares, and Eric Risch, Effects of Drought on Crop Production and Cropping Areas in Texas, *Agricultural & Environmental Letters*, February 15, 2018.
2. Anil Kumar Roy, Indira Hirway (2007), *Multiple Impacts of Droughts and Assessment of Drought Policy in Major Drought Prone States in India*, Project Report Submitted to: The Planning Commission, Government of India, New Delhi, November, 2007
3. Bhaskar K.S., Rao M.R.K., Mendhe P.N. and Suryavanshi M.R., (2005), "Micro Irrigation Management in Cotton", *CICR Technical Bulletin* No: 31, pp.39-40.
4. Karunakaran K.R., & Palanisami K., (1998), "An Analysis of Impact of Irrigation on Cropping Intensity in Tamil Nadu", *Indian Economic Review*, Vol. XXXIII, No. 2, pp. 207-220.
5. Dhawan B. D. & Harsharan Singh Datta, (1992), "Impact of Irrigation on Multiple Cropping", *EPW*, Vol. 27, No. 13, (March 28), pp. A15-A18.
6. *Economic Survey of Maharashtra 2019-20 & 2022-23*
7. *Aurangabad District Socio-Economic Review, 2020.*
8. <http://www.krishi.maharashtra.gov.in>
9. <http://agricoop.nic.in/agriculturecontingency/maharashtra>
10. <http://krishi.maharashtra.gov.in/1238/District-Level>